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Machine Literacy Among Lateral East A Irrigators Association Farmers: Current Implementation of RCEF Mechanization and Extension

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Abstract

This case study investigates the implementation of Republic Act No. 11203, otherwise known as the Rice Tariffication Law, specifically the implementation under the Rice Competitiveness Enhancement Fund (RCEF), the Rice Mechanization program, and the Rice Extension program. Issues with machine literacy stood out during data collection, which explains why the farmers do not easily adopt mechanization due to their reliance on a handful of operators and the lack of working knowledge of operating the machinery. Data was collected in the form of qualitative information from the point of view of the members of the Lateral East A Irrigators Association; furthermore, key informant interviews were conducted with the Provincial Agriculture Office of Leyte and the Municipal Agriculture Office of Alang-alang. Beyond training, there is an issue with the compensation of the machinery for smallholder farmers, which even includes members of RCEF-accredited Farmers' Cooperatives and Associations who can struggle considering the impact of the farmgate price of unmilled rice. The current association can barely mechanize their production due to the low number of production machinery and post-harvest machinery. Moving forward, more intervention must be done to properly mechanize rice production to compete with the unlimited rice imports.

Keywords: *Rice Competitiveness Enhancement Fund, Rice Tariffication Law, Rice Mechanization, Agriculture Extension, Rice Machine Literacy, Farmers Cooperative and Association, Import Liberalization, Smallholder Rice Farmer, Palay*

INTRODUCTION

The Philippines is predominantly an agrarian economy, considering that the majority of the poor work in the agriculture sector (Balisacan, 1993; Côté, 2010; Perez, 2015). Mechanization, if done right, will benefit the many, as it will shift from a labor-intensive form of production to a capital-intensive form of production for palay farming, and it may even lead to finally exporting high-value rice. However, there are some issues with RCEF as reflected in the data collected in this case study.

The Rice Competitiveness Enhancement Fund (RCEF) is wholly funded by the tariffication of rice. After a long history of imposing import restrictions on rice, the Philippines enacted the Republic Act No. 11203 (Rice Tariffication Law or RTL) to liberalize rice trade. The liberalization of the rice trade in the Philippines can provide productive gains in palay production when there is adequate investment given by the government to the rice farmers (Briones et al., 2018; Laiprakobsup, 2019). However, there are issues with RTL such as machine

literacy, inadequacy in training, RCEF did not adequately offset the unlimited importation, the liberalization of rice developed the issue of rice trade collusion, and the income for the rice farmers being affected due to low palay gate price (Cayetano et al. 2023; Clapano, 2024; Rebojo et al. 2023; Rebualos et al. 2021).

Frameworks addressing trade liberalization in Southeast Asia position rice tariffication policy mechanisms as legislative trends to address food supply uncertainties in countries with large or predominant agrarian communities undergoing transitory economic processes, which open domestic markets to western states (Warr, 2014). Moreover, following movements to liberalize the rice trade in the region, policy supplementations emerged to establish robust market-engaged institutions to safeguard local rice markets (Kim & Ramirez, 2014). Said reforms confer advantages such as a decrease in retail prices and a positive rice supply, but it also challenges local farmers to compete with the liberalized market despite the advent of rice funds from tariffs, which could double rural poverty rates in rice-producing states (Hoang & Meyers, 2015).

In spite of the legislative trend in Southeast Asia to liberalize trade in rice, the region's dichotomized nature as both large rice-exporting and rice-importing countries creates opposing responses to the trend. Importing SEA nations impose tariffs to focus development of rice production amid seasonal rice crises, while rice-exporting countries stimulate the liberalized market backed by state-owned enterprises. Existing observations on the rice trade in Southeast Asia project a distorted and inefficient market despite the expectations on rice liberalization to result in increased global benefits (Kim & Ramirez, 2014).

Politics within the processes of rice liberalization and mechanization through tariff funds to improve rice production emerged during interactions of extension workers from the municipal and national government with local cooperative leaders in Alang-alang, Leyte, on exchanges involving resources such as machines and farm inputs from the agricultural institutions, often resulting in internal arrangements and priority favors for specific cooperatives in the locale. Unpacking the implications of this phenomenon affords an analysis of the Patron-Client framework as a parallel to the phenomenon involving informal dyadic clientelist relationships (Lande, 1968; Stokes et al., 2013). The said clientelist exchanges primarily offer tactical distributions that are not public and are under personal distributive politics. (Stokes et al., 2013). Moreover, clientelist dyadic relationships involved in resource distribution processes impede the proper resource system and result in control (Chuan Yean, 2018). The clientelist framework is often evident in rural innovation efforts, specifically in monopolistic access by individuals in rural agrarian communities to incapacitate agricultural independence with low-level mechanization or diminishing technological capital investment (Roniger, 1983).

The scope of this research is limited to the Municipality of Alang-alang, Leyte, as there was an incidence of a lack of awareness of RTL, particularly by a Farmers Cooperative Association (FCA), particularly the MAALSADA cooperative; thus, other FCAs must be investigated to evaluate their machine literacy and look for other problems with RCEF (Cayetano et al., 2023; Longo et al., 2023). The current study sought to examine the mechanization and extension program of RCEF; therefore, the seed and financial program are excluded.

Statement of the Problem

Based on the literature, particularly by Longno et al. (2023) and Cayetano et al. (2023), there are discrepancies in RCEF. The issue of machine literacy and awareness must be addressed to realize the benefits of mechanization for all farmers. According to prior data, it necessitates an investigation in the Alang-alang area on the matter of the

implementation of RCEF, with how the extension agents extend their aid to the beneficiaries and how the institutions that implement RCEF. The researchers sought to answer the following:

1. What is the idea of rice farmers on the connection between the RCEF mechanization program and the RCEF extension program?
2. How did the rice farmers engage with the agricultural extension workers?
3. What experiences do rice farmers share about the difficulties they face in becoming aware of and participating in the RCEF program?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This study employs a qualitative approach, specifically an explanatory single-case study based on the outcome process tracing framework explained by Beach and Pedersen (2013). This approach is appropriate for analyzing complex, real-world interventions where quantitative methods provide limited explanatory depth (George & Bennett, 2005; Yin, 2018).

The researchers selected Lateral East A Irrigators Association (Lateral East) as the case of the current research project. Lateral East serves as the appropriate organization to be examined, as they have received machinery from the year of 2022, which includes post-harvest machinery and production machinery such as tractors and combine-harvesters.

Research Locale. The study was conducted in Alang-alang, Leyte, which was selected for its relevance to RCEF implementation and gaps in existing literature (Longno et al., 2023). The specific barangay from which data was taken is Barangay Hubang due to the number of Lateral East members in the same government unit.

Research Participants. The population of the study includes the members of the Lateral East; while there are at least 400 members, 6 participants will be taken, as the number was sufficient enough to generate themes and reach data saturation for a single-case qualitative study. To be included in the case study, farmers must have the following:

1. Member of Lateral East;
2. Registered with the Registry System for the Basic Sectors in Agriculture (RSBSA);
3. Must be willing to participate.

Individuals who do not meet the criteria are excluded. Beyond conducting interviews with farmers, the researchers reached out to the agricultural officers to act as a form of triangulation. These key informants take part in the "elite interview," which includes an officer from the provincial agriculture office (PAO) and the municipal agriculture office (MAO). Taking information from these participants is important to give the required context and validation to the responses of the farmer-participants (Beach & Pederson, 2013). Participant selection followed qualitative standards of relevance, data saturation, and thematic adequacy (Yin, 2018; Braun & Clarke, 2019).

Research Instrument. The study utilized an in-depth, semi-structured interview guide for rice farmers and key officers in Alang-alang, Leyte. The guide consisted of open-ended questions aligned with the research questions and was designed to elicit detailed accounts of RCEF information dissemination and extension practices.

There are two parts of the instrument, which includes the question for the farmer-participant, and the second part is meant for participants who partake in the elite interview to answer. Pilot testing was conducted in Carigara, Leyte, which is a municipality that shares similar characteristics with the current research locale. The instrument was further validated by at least three experts in the fields of research and political science, and necessary revisions were made prior to data collection.

Sampling Procedure. The researchers used a non-probability sampling method, specifically convenience sampling with a purposive criterion. The farmer-participants were selected according to the inclusion criteria and were recruited by a Lateral East member. Finally, officers were selected according to their involvement in RCEF, and their ability during the implementation of RCEF was considered to be included in the semi-structured interview.

Data Collection Procedure. The study collected data through individual interviews with RSBSA-registered rice farmers who met the inclusion criteria. The researchers first identified a case that fit the research objectives through a screening process, following Yin (2018), and coordinated with the municipal agriculture office to engage with the correct FCAs. Data collection combined interviews, observations, and document review to allow triangulation and improve validity and reliability (Beach & Pedersen, 2013; Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Yin, 2018).

1. **Interviews.** The current case study conducted a combination of non-elite and elite individual interviews in the desired language of the participants, and audio recordings were gathered, provided that consent was given (Beach & Pedersen, 2013; Yin, 2018). Researchers followed the Leyte Normal University (University) sanctioned protocols for interviews, which require an Informed Consent Form (ICF) approved by the ethics board. Interviews were done in the comfort of the homes of the farmer-participants and in the offices of agricultural officers.
2. **Observations.** While the interviewers take on the passive role during data collection, behavior was observed during the interview, and the environment was taken into consideration (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Yin, 2018). Provided that consent was given, the researchers took photographs of the surroundings of the research locale as a form of evidence to validate the findings made during the interview.
3. **Documents.** The researchers gathered "archival documents" to inform them during the interview, and they were gathered with the consent of the organization, specifically the Lateral East Association, MAO, and PAO (Beach & Pedersen, 2013; Yin, 2018). It is important to ensure the authenticity of the documents prior to usage for the case study. However, the current research documents were utilized for the screening of the FCAs, and they merely inform the interviewers during data collection.

Data Triangulation. The collection of interview data, observational data, and documents is important to ensure validity and credibility of the data (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Beach & Pedersen, 2013; Yin, 2018). All these forms of data were collected and used to validate each other for the current study.

Research Reflexivity. To minimize bias, reflexivity was employed, and research notes were taken to take note of the events that may sway data collection (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). After data collection, every event that may influence the data was reported to the research panel, and they are present in the current study to inform the readers of the events that occurred in data collection.

Ethical Consideration. Prior to data collection, the researchers took part in an ethical review by the University to ensure the safety of the participants through conducting a review of the manuscript and the ICF by the review board. Researchers followed the data privacy protocols, and there was no funding to conduct this research.

Data Analysis. Audio recordings were collected and converted to text transcripts to gather themes. The researchers systematically coded the transcripts using open coding, allowing patterns and meanings to emerge directly from the data. Thematic analysis according to Braun and Clarke (2018) was used to conduct the data analysis, which essentially looks for codes and generates themes taken from the systematically recognized codes from the transcript.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Through the researcher-constructed semi-structured instruments, the researchers have gathered themes. The researchers have found that there was an **impact of the machine usage**, there were **problems related to operation with the machinery**, and there were **issues with machine literacy**.

1. Machine usage. Among the major uses of farm machinery were the tractors and rice-combine harvesters. According to the respondents, it did improve palay production for the Association, but it was evident from the responses that they only make use of the production machinery over the post-harvest machinery such as the grain dryer and rice miller. With one respondent saying that they could not even utilize the rice millers because it was a faulty "prototype" made by PhilRice. The Association does make use of the given grain dryers, but palay for personal consumption was instead sun-dried. While the machinery did provide productive results during the production of palay, it did not result in the utilization of post-harvest machinery, particularly the rice miller; thus, the Association can only produce dried palay as their product.

2. Problems related to the operation of the machinery. Among the complaints made by the farmer respondents was the unsuitability of production machinery in some of the rice parcels, citing possible delays with production due to broken-down equipment because of deep rice paddies and roads being faulty. There are also issues with limited equipment; farmers state that the Association would typically loan their farm equipment to other farmers. Furthermore, some respondents cite that the maintenance of the farm machinery is an issue due to the availability of spare parts and service centers for farm vehicles. Some farmers state that they could not operate the "rice transplanters," which will quickly transplant germinated seeds to the rice paddy without requiring labor. Many participants would prefer to hire labor to plant the rice. For this theme, there are issues that RCEF could not address; despite demonstrations made by extension agents or experts, farmer respondents could not fully realize the potential of these machines, namely the rice transplanter, where labor was even used to plant the seeds. What transpired from the interview reveals that the farm equipment did not fit the circumstances of the farmers, and furthermore, investment in the rice production industry is required to have a proper ecosystem that will effectively implement rice mechanization.

3. Machine literacy. Farmer members will only rely on their representatives to gain information on machine use. Further, the farmer respondents relied on hiring farm operators, which will lead to potential delays with production due to unavailability of operators. Farmers cite that there were delays for production because the "driver" of the tractors was not available at the time. Mastery of the machines is required to realize effective implementation of RCEF, according to Cayetano et al. (2023). What is revealed from the interviews shows that the institutions that provide the extension for RCEF are inadequate for mechanization.

What can be inferred from the results are the inadequacies of the institution that supports RCEF. While there is a law that extends RCEF, particularly Republic Act No. 12078, further studies are required to develop the institutions that implement mechanization. Farmers

lost P13 billion for the year 2019 due to the liberalization of rice, and based on prices of rice, it amounted to 43 to 50 pesos per kilo, with the farmgate price of palay at 24.70 pesos per kilo (Dizon et al., 2023; Gomez, 2024). Due to the inability to produce well-milled white rice by the regular farmers, this will not result in improvements for the income of smallholder rice farmers. To effectively offset this, FCAs must be equipped with the working knowledge of operating rice mills to enable the production of high-value commodities to not rely on established rice millers and to not only produce dry palay as their commodity. The reliance on labor must be reduced to properly implement mechanization.

Clientelism plays a role in disrupting the mechanization of rice production where the grants of machines are selected for particular FCAs as a means to elevate a politician's chances in elections through a dyadic relationship (Aspinall & Berenschot, 2019; Chuan Yean, 2017; Lande, 1968). What can be inferred from the interviews is that the implementation of RCEF is purely top-down in nature, which will give way to patronage to occur, where farmers are given just enough to slightly improve income. Instead of instituting authorities determining the distribution of machines, there must be a bottom-up framework from which it can provide to the particular needs of every farmer (Homsy et al., 2018). This requires academic rigor of the local environment and political will to properly mechanize rice production.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Cayetano et al. (2023), and Longno et al. (2023), provided the gap that the current researchers are trying to resolve. Mechanization under the current form of implementation remains inadequate, and it is not competitive with competitors from Southeast Asia, such as Vietnam and Thailand. The potential of the Philippines to compete with these rice exporters is there, given that proper handling of funds and rent-seeking politicians are reduced. Taken from the interview, the farmer respondents are open to grants from the government; however, machine usage is lacking due to machine illiteracy. The Philippines must institute a structure where it encourages a bottom-up framework of mechanization where it seeks insights from academics, NGOs, LGUs, and farmers as a form of reference to improve the livelihood and compete in the rice trade.

To resolve this issue, more research needs to be done to properly capture the institution of RCEF and improve the institution to encourage industrialization and mechanization in the rice production sector of agriculture. The Philippines needs to institutionalize a rice industry that produces white rice instead of palay in large quantities. The legislative department needs to look for improvements to be made for RCEF and make it a long-term legislative project. The executive department needs to implement a proper national policy that gives effective mechanization in palay production and makes white rice a viable trading commodity to compete with Southeast Asian countries such as Vietnam and Thailand.

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